

PERCEIVED EFFECTIVENESS OF SCHOOL LEARNING ACTION CELLS (SLAC) ON THE PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT OF SECONDARY SCHOOL TEACHERS: ENHANCED SLAC PLAN

Annotation:

This study investigated the impact of the School Learning Action Cell (SLAC) on the professional development of secondary school teachers in the District of Carmen, Division of Cebu Province. Findings revealed that most respondents possessed master's units (75.36%) and had been teaching for 11–20 years (35.50%). Teachers generally perceived SLAC sessions as highly positive ($M = 4.57$, on a scale of 1 to 5, with 5 being “Highly Positive”). The effects on professional development were rated as Highly Effective ($M = 4.44$), particularly in improving lesson delivery, reflective teaching, and learner-centered instruction. ANOVA results indicated significant differences in perception when grouped by educational attainment ($p = 0.020$) and years of experience ($p = 0.003$), but not by the number of sessions attended ($p = 0.596$). Moreover, a strong positive correlation was found between teachers' perceptions and the effects of professional development ($r = 0.766$, $p < 0.001$). The null hypotheses were rejected, as there were significant differences across educational attainment and teaching experience, as well as significant positive relationships between perceptions and outcomes. The study concluded that SLAC sessions had a significant impact on enhancing teacher competence and promoting school improvement. Recommendations included strengthening participation and contextualization of LAC activities and conducting longitudinal studies to explore long-term effects on teaching performance and student outcomes. An enhanced School Learning Action Cell program was developed as an output of this study.

Keywords:

SLAC Session, Professional Development, Department of Education, Descriptive-Correlational, Significant Relationships, Significant Difference.

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Chapter 1

THE PROBLEM AND ITS SCOPE

INTRODUCTION

Rationale of the Study

In the Department of Education (DepEd), a School Learning Action Cell (SLAC) session was a cooperative learning opportunity where educators and administrators collaborate to address common issues in their schools and enhance instruction. These workshops were a component of DepEd's larger plan for ongoing professional development, with an aim to develop and build the character, abilities, and teacher's knowledge. DepEd issued an order titled "The Learning Action Cell As A K To 12 Basic Education Program that aid to teaching and learning is a School-Based Continuing Professional Development Strategy" (DO 35, s. 2016) in relation to the Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013 (Republic Act Number [R. A. No.] 10533, 2013).

The Learning Action Cell (LAC) was added to the policy in 2016 as part of the K–12 Basic Education Program, a strategic development to enhance teaching and learning for ongoing professional development. With the help of the school principal or another authorized LAC leader, this policy sought to involve teachers in constructive, considerate, and secure coordinated synchronous group sessions to address issues faced by the school. The process was in the form of gathering the teachers handling the same subjects or grade levels once a month.

The model of the Learning Action Cell was based on extensive research into the idea of professional learning communities where experts have dubbed as the "greatest hope for recreating a school." However, a particular set of conditions had to be met for this approach to work. Dufour and Marzano (2011) listed these prerequisites as follows: (1) high standards of learning for all students the school must highlight; (2) teachers collaborate into teams or groups; (3) teams must offer a guaranteed curriculum for every course and grade level; (4) teachers develop assessments common to all; and (5) for continuous learning improvement, an evidence-based student learning must be developed (Humada-Ludeke, 2013).

The United Nations Educational, Scientific, and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) states that in order to satisfy the government's and the public's demands for high-quality education, educators must be reflective, change-oriented, and sensitive to the dynamic personalities of their students. This situation made clear how important it is for educators to continue their professional development in order to improve the teaching-learning process and, as a result, raise educational standards. According to the 2010 Department of Education (DepEd) Discussion Paper on K–12, teachers are essential to the Philippines' Basic Education, which aims to support students' growth and development.

Participants in SLAC were given an opportunity to communicate their understanding of teaching material and practice through open dialogue. Additionally, these allowed teachers to share their best practices among others, to plan and prepare classes, and as well as to reflect on those lessons they commonly shared; it was advised that this must be included in teachers' timetables (Madigan & Scroth-Cavataio, 2011).

On the other hand, In-service training (INSET) for teachers had usually been conducted during Mid-year and Summer, but school-based learning action cells (LACs) were also given minute attention in some schools, affecting the Key Performance Indicators (KPI) of schools. Despite the week-long training of teachers before they were immersed in the new curriculum, some skills were still lacking in the delivery of the new curriculum (Drago, 2017).

Various topics were covered during SLAC sessions; these subjects were common problems that existed in the school and teaching practices, and culture that required immediate attention. The researcher was

prompted to pursue this study because many teachers failed to apply their skills and the learning, they gained from SLAC sessions. Further, the researcher wanted to investigate whether these SLACs, regularly conducted in their respective schools helped in their professional growth and development.

Consequently, instructional design for educators and learners improved understanding by utilizing them in realistic conditions. In a local setting SLAC sessions were conducted monthly in schools by school administrators such as the school principals and master teachers. There were no concrete or uniform topics to discussed during LAC sessions.

The purpose of the study was to determine how well the School Learning Action Cell (SLAC) sessions helped teachers in the Carmen District improve their professional skills. The sought to understand how these SLAC sessions affect their teaching ability and growth as teachers. The study examined the understanding of the extent of the effectiveness of the SLAC teachers to their professional development. Ultimately, the results were meant to help develop a better SLAC plan that meets the teachers' professional needs and goals.

Theoretical Background

The "Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013" (RA 10533, 2013) and "The Learning Action Cell As A K To 12 Basic Education Program School-Based Continuing Professional Development Strategy for the Improvement of Teaching and Learning" (DO 35, 2016) served as the legal foundations for this study, which was based on the collaborative learning theory of Lev Vygotsky, constructivist philosophy/theory of Jean Piaget, and adult learning theory.

Teachers as adult learners collaboratively constructed their own learning for professional development. Thus, this research anchored on the Collaborative learning theory of Lev Vygotsky, Constructivist Philosophy/Theory of Jean Piaget, and Adult Learning Theory by Knowles.

The *Collaborative Learning Theory* by Lev Vygotsky supported this presentation that was developed in 1978 as its theoretical framework. The idea that learning is a social activity served as the foundation for this paradigm. Vgotsky advocated a sociocultural perspective on cognitive development that combined social context for learning with individual learning. The objectivist perspective on the other hand where instruction was allocated and independent learning occurred, the collaborative perspectives played a more active role in the learners' learning process.

According to Fullan (2001), schools had a collaborative atmosphere, Teachers who engaged in discourse became aware of the various methods and approaches available, and they actively placed themselves in both possible and present practice. This theory signified the importance of collaboration between the school administrator and teachers in administering the School Learning Action Cell to address learning gaps and enrich best practices.

For the *Constructivist Philosophy/Theory* of Jean Piaget, According to Gray (2005) and Desta et al. (2014), continuing professional development (CPD) was originally introduced in the middle of the 1970s. Constructivist philosophy and theory, which held that a person's worldview and breakthroughs were dynamic and always changing, served as the foundation for its notion. It was consequently believed that instructors needed to actively plan and regularly carry out their professional development in order to deal with ongoing change. Numerous models have been employed to address research in teacher professional development. Among them was the Learning Action Cell model (LAC). Teachers supported one another and continued to learn as they implement these improvements in the classroom through Learning Action Cell (LAC) workshops.

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

Constructivism was an epistemology, a philosophy of knowledge or interpretation, that provided an explanation of the origins of knowledge and the process of human learning. Only the prior experiences and background knowledge of the learners were used to build the true comprehension. The theory posited that people generated unique comprehensions or insights by combining their preexisting beliefs with the concepts, incidents, and experiences they encountered. In order to help students develop their own ideas, opinions, and conclusions, teachers served as mentors, facilitators, and co-explorers (Ciot, 2009).

As to the *Adult Learning Theory*, this was often known as andragogy, was created by Malcolm Knowles in 1968. It examined how adult learning differed from that of children. It tried to highlight the unique features of adult learning and pointed out the learning styles that were most effective for them.

Legal bases. This study was supported by the DepEd order titled *The Learning Action Cell as a K to 12 Basic Education Program School-Based Continuing Professional Development Strategy for the Improvement of Teaching and Learning* (DO 35, 2016). The DepEd was also aware of how much the caliber of teaching affects the caliber of learning. Therefore, the DepEd hired competent teachers and provided for their professional growth. In order to adapt old beliefs and assumptions about education,

community, teaching, and learning to meet the requirements of today's students, professional learning communities helped teachers build new knowledge about instruction. Additionally, the Third Elementary Education Project (TEEP), Secondary Education Development and Improvement Project (SEDIP), Program for Decentralized Education (PRODED), and empirical studies on comparable professional development programs that demonstrated that teachers' involvement in professional development activities has a positive impact on teachers' beliefs served as affirmative bases for this policy (UNESCO ISO, 2006).

The DepEd directive "The Learning Action Cell As a K To 12 Basic Education Program School-Based Continuing Professional Development Strategy for the Improvement of Teaching and Learning" reaffirmed that teachers may select the subjects for LAC sessions with the principal's or LAC leader's general approval. This may be achieved by carrying out a needs assessment, the findings of which assisted the LAC in determining their top learning priorities (DO 35, 2016). The LAC may cover a wide range of topics, such as curriculum, methodology, and learner diversity and inclusion.

According to Oakley et al. (2018), the SLAC sessions were thought to be the most cost-effective continuing professional development process that improved teaching-learning processes that improved student learning, developed successful teachers, enabled teachers to support one another in improving their content and pedagogical knowledge, practice, skills, and attitudes, and fostered a professional collaborative spirit among school administrators, teachers, and the community at large.

The initiative's purpose and rationale were outlined in the enabling DepEd order 35, 2016, "The Learning Action Cell: A School-Based Continuing Professional Development Approach for Enhancing Teaching and Learning in K–12 Basic Education Programs," which also highlighted the necessity of continuing school-based learning for successful teacher development and the necessity of school-based conferences, seminars, and events to improve teacher mass training (DO 35, 2016). Thus, the goal of this study was to assist teachers in determining whether the material offered in school-based LAC sessions was sufficiently and successfully utilized for their own professional growth.

The DepEd also emphasized that teaching effectiveness may have an impact on learning quality. This implies that DepEd needs to hire exceptionally competent lecturers. In order to address the needs of today's students, professional learning communities were established to support educators in developing new knowledge about teaching and rewriting conventional beliefs about teaching, community, and education (Little, 2005).

This policy was supported by the Third Elementary Education Project (TEEP), the Secondary Education Development and Improvement Project (SEDIP), the Program for Decentralized Education (PRODED), and empirical research on the same professional training programs. These research demonstrated the beneficial effects of teachers' involvement in professional development activities on their practices and attitudes, students' learning, and the execution of educational reforms (UNESCO ISO 2006).

Effective teachers, according to Stronge (2007),: 1) possess a thorough understanding of the subject matter that they can translate into sound learning objectives; 2) are able to select and employ the best teaching strategies and resources to teach the identified content objectives; 3) base their instructional decisions on the results of formative assessments; 4) genuinely support their students' learning and overall development; and 5) carry out their work in a professional and ethical manner.

Teachers had access to and opportunity for both kinds of professional development programs thanks to effective educational institutions (Whitehouse 2011). Therefore, within the framework of School-Based Management (SBM), which is reflected in the SIPs, the DepEd has an obligation to offer teachers' ongoing professional development (CPD). As a result, deliberate steps became the focal point of learner development in the school's student learning experiences.

A DepEd Learning Action Cell was a group of teachers who took part in cooperative learning sessions facilitated by the school's principal or a LAC specialist to solve common issues the school faced. LACs will grow into school-based communities of practice that are secure, encouraging, and productive (D.O. 35, 2016).

LAC session topics. Ongoing cooperative awareness of school challenges within a common interest in professional development, self-directed approach, reflective practice that resulted in action and self-evaluation, and collective capacities and skills were key ideas of the process. The aims of this policy were as follows: One. to enhance the teaching-learning process, which will result in better student learning; 2. to develop effective educators; 3. to allow educators to assist one another in continuously enhancing their pedagogical and subject knowledge, practice, abilities, and attitudes; and 4. to cultivate a spirit of professional collaboration among educators, school administrators, and the community at large (D.O. 35, 2016).

The school head who initiated the program supervised the faculty's selection of the subjects discussed in LAC sessions. The issues will be determined and prioritized during the session through needs assessment. A few important conclusions from the K–12 Basic Education Program were given particular attention. The themes must be in line with the characteristics of the K–12 Basic Education Program as outlined in Republic Act (R.A.) No. 10533, the Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013, and in a number of DepEd policies. The following general topics must be covered:

Learner diversity and student inclusion. Learner diversity and student inclusion throughout the LAC sessions should be prioritized since they are the foundation of all educational processes, and successful teachers understood and cared for the students they serve. Teachers' primary responsibility became creating learning settings that catered to a diverse group of learners. It emphasized how important it is for teachers to comprehend the traits and experiences of their students. The phrase "diversity" refers to a wide range of characteristics, including gender, special needs, community belonging, religious, and familial values. Teachers that support student variety made modifications and used various learning approaches to accommodate these variations. Additionally, the regulations mandated that teachers provide remedial classes for learners who were having difficulty comprehending what was being taught. The intervention encouraged students to communicate effectively and helped avert failure.

The K–12 Basic Education Program's content and pedagogy. Teachers were more at ease creating lesson plans for the K–12 programs because they had more strategies and expertise at their disposal. Teachers who are prepared and self-assured can implement developmentally appropriate teaching methods that take into account the unique requirements and characteristics of each student. Additionally, teachers could collaborate with students to design learning objectives. To effectively organize lessons, confidently give instructions, and evaluate student progress, teachers must be proficient in both content standards and learning competencies.

They might work with teachers to develop weekly lessons during the LAC sessions that they can use for a set amount of time in order to observe the improvement in their lessons. Teachers' capacity to translate material into relevant learning experiences increases dramatically as their critical, creative, and higher order thinking skills are strengthened. As teachers become more methodical in their instructional planning and more adept at contextualizing and addressing learners' varied requirements, students' learning will simultaneously improve.

The K–12 Basic Education Program's Assessment and Reporting. The K–12 Curriculum's learner-centered assessment policies should be understood by all educators. Lesson discussions should inevitably cover how to evaluate students' learning and how formative assessment data can enhance subsequent instruction. Teachers and students receive the essential input regarding learning outcomes through assessment. Teachers are able to continuously choose, arrange, and employ effective assessment procedures thanks to this feedback, which also informs the reporting cycle.

ICT Integration and 21st Century Skills in Education and Evaluation. Creating a link between 21st century skills and the teaching and learning process is the main goal of the K–12 Basic Education Program. Information and communications technology (ICT) must be adopted by teachers in order to enhance their classes and make instruction easier. Most significantly, ICT made the procedures of learning and assessment easier. In this generation, it is expected that teachers are well-versed in the usage of information and communication technology.

Curriculum Indigenization, Localization, and Contextualization. Curriculum contextualization is the practice of aligning curriculum content with instructional learning strategies that are pertinent to students. Teachers frequently take into account the diversity of their students by implementing differentiated instruction in their lesson plans. Teachers must recognize and seize chances to connect relevant teaching and learning experiences, interests, and goals for a larger school community and engagement with stakeholders.

If local experiences are connected to new material and are familiar to students, learning will be significant and unforgettable. Contextualization is one of the K–12 curriculum's most important features. The resources for students and the teacher's handbook may be altered to take into account the individual circumstances of a certain area (D.O. 35, 2016).

On the other hand, adult learning, sometimes referred to as andragogy, may aid in the creation of teachers' professional development plans when paired with CPTD (Continuous Professional Teacher Development). Merriam and Bierema (2014) asserted that andragogy ought to be an important theory, model, or method for understanding and structuring education for adult learners. The establishment of learning opportunities and environments was facilitated by adult learning ideas (Gregson & Sturko, 2007).

According to Silva's (2018) study, "School Learning Action Cell as a Key for Teachers' Continuous Learning and Development," teachers need to expand their training in a number of areas, including diversity and inclusive education, content and pedagogy, evaluation and reporting, 21st century skills, and better ICT integration and contextualization of lessons. Prioritizing themes and creating LAC materials were two issues that arose during SLAC. The results of a similar study by Correos and Paler (2020) regarding the Extent of Implementation, In the 37 districts of Surigao del Sur Division, 249 school heads and 3,907 teachers participated in the Monitoring and Evaluation of School Learning Action Cell (SLAC) as a Cost-effective Learning and Development Strategy for Teachers Development. The results showed that while teachers' comprehension of SLAC as a way to improve instructional delivery was fair, school administrators' and teachers' understanding was also fair. The findings demonstrated that instructors' knowledge of how to implement school learning action cells was inadequate.

On the other hand, Culajara (2022) revealed that LAC sessions helped the teacher in monitoring students' data and achievement through varied activities and constant communication by enhancing their skills and knowledge. Moreover, to succeed in addressing the needs related to school improvement and learning development, the Learning Action Cell (LAC) requires substantial reflection and careful planning to effectively respond to teachers' needs and support students' academic achievement through this professional practice.

According to Desta, Chalchisa, and Lemma (2014), the skills and information acquired through teacher professional development are essential for lessening the problems that educators face on a regular basis in their current position. They improved teaching-learning situations, kept up-to-date, cutting-edge teaching materials, and helped create an effective learning environment by participating in these workshops, which pushed them to become better educators in the modern world (Briones & Felipe, 2013). Cohen and Hill (2000) found that teachers who adhered to professional development approaches were studying directly relevant to the subject matter they would be instructing.

The learning environment was enhanced by CPTD that was dynamic and interactive and focused on the social aspect of adult learning in peer groups (Zepeda, 2008). Planning for CPTD should therefore take this social aspect of adult learning into consideration. Hargreaves and Fullan (2001) asserted that continuous professional development was necessary for both the individual teacher and the groups of teachers engaged in peer learning activities in order to facilitate effective teaching and learning.

THE PROBLEM

Statement of the Problem

This research assessed the effectiveness of the conduct of School Learning Action Cell (SLAC) sessions on the professional development of teachers of Carmen District - Cebu Province during the school year 2024-2025 as the basis for an SLAC enhancement plan.

Specifically, the study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the respondents' teachers, in terms of:
 - 1.1. Highest educational attainment;
 - 1.2. Number of years in service, and
 - 1.3. Number of SLAC sessions attended?
2. What are the teacher's perceptions about the conduct of the SLAC sessions?
3. What are the perceived effectiveness of the SLAC on the teachers' respondents in terms of:
 - 3.1. Teaching Practice
 - 3.2. Professional development;
 - 3.3. Student learning; and
 - 3.4. Overall SLAC effectiveness?
4. Is there a significant difference between the overall effectiveness of the conduct of SLAC against their educational attainment, years of teaching, and number of SLAC sessions attended?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the teachers' perceptions on the conduct of SLAC sessions to the perceived effectiveness on teachers' development, professional development, student learning, and overall SLAC effectiveness?
6. Based on the findings of the study, what enhanced SLAC plan can be proposed?

Statement of the Null Hypotheses

H₀₁: There was no significant difference between teachers' perceptions on the conduct of SLAC and their educational attainment, years of teaching, and number of SLAC sessions attended.

H₀₂: There was no significant relationship between the teachers' perceptions about the conduct of SLAC sessions and the effects of the SLAC on the teacher-respondents' professional development.

Significance of the Study

The study aimed to assess the effectiveness of the implementation of School Learning Action Cell (SLAC) sessions to teachers' professional development. The result of this study will be beneficial to the following sectors and entities.

Teachers. The study suggested that SLAC sessions helped teachers think critically, connect with each other, and improve as professionals. Teachers improved their comprehension of the curriculum and come up with innovative methods to teach that make lessons more effective by establishing structured learning communities.

Learners. Students were the ones who benefited the most from teachers performing more of what they do. As teachers improved their teaching methods through SLAC, students were more likely to get lessons that were responsive, interesting, and in line with their academic needs. Thereby leading to better learning results.

School Administrators. The findings helped school leaders understand the importance of having regular and organized SLAC meetings. With this data, school administrators might better support their teachers by giving them the resources they need, coaching them, and making sure they work in an environment that encourages them to keep learning.

Department of Education (DepEd). The analysis of this study provided DepEd practical proof for strengthening teacher development programs across the country. The results helped shape policies and frameworks that aimed toward making excellent SLAC practices an ongoing component of schools as a way to improve the quality of teaching.

The Researcher. Through the study, the researcher learned a lot about how SLAC implementation works and what happens as a result of this investigation. The information gained by the researcher not only helped her do better in school, but it gave her the power to push for evidence-based improvements in education.

Future Researchers. This study was a starting point for more academic research on professional learning communities in schools. It opened the doors for future research to investigate related areas, including SLAC's long-term effects, how it can be scaled up, or how it can be combined with other teacher development programs.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research design, study flow, environment, respondents, instrument, data collection, statistical analysis of the data, and scoring process are all covered in this section.

Design

Descriptive a correlational study a quantitative technique that examines the relationship or link between two or more variables, was used in this study. In evaluating the impact of School Learning Action Cell (SLAC) sessions on the professional development of teachers in Carmen District, Cebu Province, during the academic year 2024–2025, the research design is pertinent. Information about the respondents' profiles, including their years of service, highest level of education, and number of SLAC sessions attended, were gathered and presented using the descriptive portion of the design.

The correlational aspect sought to find out how variables were related to each other and how they differed from each other. For example, the study looked at the differences and similarities between teachers' views of SLAC and how it affected their professional development, as well as between their views and their demographic profiles. This aspect of the design allowed the researcher used statistics to see if differences in years of service, educational level, or number of SLAC sessions attended were strongly linked to how people feel about SLAC implementation.

Flow of the Study

Figure 2 shows the flow of the study. This section encompassed the following: inputs to be studied, process, and output.

Input. The demographic profile of the respondents, including their years of service, degree of education, and number of SLAC sessions attended, served as the study's input. Additionally, teachers' perceptions of how often they used the learning action cell sessions, how SLAC affected their professional development in terms of teaching methods, the variety of student demands, and evaluation and assessment.

Process. The study collected, analyzed, and interpreted data for the variables to be measured in order to draw conclusions and suggestions.

Output. The study's conclusions will serve as the foundation for suggested improvements to the SLAC program.

Figure 2. *Flow of the Study*

This study was conducted at the Carmen District, Division of Cebu Province schools. Carmen was located in the northeastern part of Cebu province and was a coastal municipality comprising 21 barangays. Recognized as the business hub of northern Cebu, it hosted a mix of both public and private educational institutions that catered to the needs of the local population.

The district of Carmen had 20 elementary and 6 secondary schools. To fully capture a meaningful result, the secondary school teachers of the Carmen district participated. At least 200 teachers participated, except for the chosen group for pilot testing. The researcher chose the district of Carmen because it is where she has served for several years.

Figure 3. *Location Map of the Research Environment*

Respondents

The study's respondents were the secondary teachers in the schools district of Carmen. They themselves primarily had the first-hand information regarding LAC sessions. The entire population of 168, including 30 respondents for pilot testing of secondary school teachers were the target respondents. They were chosen because they were the primary source of data regarding the implementation of the SLAC.

Table 1. *Distribution of Respondents*

SCHOOLS	n	%
Carmen NHS-Day	126	75
Caurasan NHS	8	4.76
Cantumog NHS	30	17.85
S. Duterte Integrated School	4	2.38
TOTAL	168	100

Instrument

A questionnaire developed through the researcher was used in this investigation. There were three sections to the questionnaire. The demographic profile of the respondents, including years of teaching experience, highest level of education attained, and the number of SLAC trainings attended, was covered in Part I. Part II focuses on the *teachers' perceptions of the conduct of the SLAC sessions*. Part III examined the perceived effects of SLAC on secondary school teachers' development, which further clustered into *effectiveness on teaching practice*, *effectiveness on professional development*, *effectiveness on student learning*, and the *overall effectiveness of the SLAC sessions*.

The reliability analyses conducted for the different scales in the questionnaire indicated that all sets of items demonstrate acceptable to very good internal consistency based on Cronbach's alpha values. The first scale included the *teachers' perceptions of the conduct of the SLAC sessions* items, where the computed Cronbach's alpha was 0.767. This result was higher than the typical cutoff of 0.70, indicating that the scale has acceptable internal reliability and that the items were consistently assessing the intended construct.

The second scale, composed of the *effectiveness on teaching practice* items, yielded a Cronbach's alpha of 0.874. This reflected very high internal consistency, surpassing the 0.80 benchmark typically associated with strong reliability. The alpha coefficient was not excessively high, meaning the items were consistent without being redundant. This demonstrated that the *effectiveness of teaching practice* was highly reliable for assessing the construct it aimed to measure.

Meanwhile, the third scale, which included the *effectiveness of professional development*, returned a Cronbach's alpha of 0.717. This value met the acceptable reliability threshold, indicating that the items were sufficiently consistent. However, the analysis flagged item 9 as negatively correlating with the total scale, suggesting that it might need to be reverse-coded to align with the direction of the other items. Addressing this item helped further strengthen the scale's reliability.

For the fourth scale, composed of the *effectiveness on student learning*, the reliability coefficient was 0.775, indicating good internal consistency. Similar to the previous scale, item number 4 was found to negatively correlate with the total score. This suggested that it may also require reverse-coding to correct the scoring direction and improve the overall consistency of the scale.

Lastly, the scale containing the *overall effectiveness of the SLAC sessions* produced a Cronbach's alpha of 0.780, indicated good reliability. All items in this scale demonstrated consistent measurement of the construct, with no problematic items identified. Therefore, the *overall effectiveness of the SLAC sessions* scale was suitable for use in the study without further modifications.

Overall, the results of the reliability tests showed that all five scales met or exceeded the minimum requirement for acceptable reliability. Most scales exhibited good to very high internal consistency, with only a few items requiring attention due to negative correlations. With minor adjustments, all scales were confirmed to be reliable tools for data collection in the study.

Data Gathering Procedure

The execution in the conduct of the study was covered by the research procedure. Pre-data collecting, real data gathering, and post-data gathering are the three separate stages of the methodical data collection procedure used in this study. The three stages were designed to guarantee procedural clarity, data reliability, and ethical norms.

Pre-Data Gathering Procedure. Before distributing the survey questionnaires, transmittal letters were written and sent to the appropriate authorities for approval. These were the College Dean, the Schools Division Superintendent, and the School Principals of the schools that were chosen. Once these letters were approved, they prepared written permission from the school administrators to undertake the study in their schools. The researcher started collecting data after getting all the necessary approvals of transmittal letters.

Actual Data Gathering Procedure. The self-made questionnaire was the primary tool to gather data. It was designed to gather useful information from the teacher-respondents. Before handing out the questionnaires, the researcher should meet with the teachers who were taking part to explain the study's goal, provided them with instructions on how to fill out the questionnaire, and answered any questions they may have. The consent was handed over to the participating teachers. This orientation ensured that everyone knew what the study goal was about and that their privacy would be protected. The researcher handed out the surveys and collected them back after the agreed time. To make sure the research results were accurate, everyone was asked to answer the instrument honestly and completely.

Post-Data Gathering Procedure. Once all the filled-out questionnaires had been collected, the answers were carefully sorted, counted, and categorized so they could be analyzed. To keep the data safe and private, the raw data will be kept in a digital repository that was secure, and only the researcher could access it. The data were kept in a locked physical storage space. Once the data had been thoroughly processed, meaning it had been examined and interpreted in line with the study's goals, any physical documents were safely shredded, and digital copies were deleted using established ethical disposal methods to keep the respondents' identity's anonymous.

Statistical treatment

The study examined its data using both descriptive and inferential statistics. Descriptive statistics such as frequency counts, percentages, means, and standard deviations are used to summarize the profiles of the teacher-respondents, including their highest level of education, years of employment, and number of SLAC sessions attended, as well as their perceptions of the way SLAC sessions are conducted and how they affect their professional development. These actions will facilitate the observation and comprehension of the sample's central patterns and data trends.

For inferential statistics, the appropriate tests used to look at the differences and correlations between variables. The study used Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) to assess the significant differences of the variables in order to determine whether there were significant differences in teacher perceptions based on their demographic profiles. Conversely, the Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient (Pearson r) was used to examine the relationship between teacher perceptions of how SLAC sessions were conducted and their impact on professional development. These statistical tools helped the researcher make sense of the data and helped them come up with a data-driven plan to improve SLAC.

Scoring Procedure

A scoring procedure utilized to quantify the gathered data. This could be seen herein. A 5-point Likert scaling below was used to determine their responses based on level of agreement, level of evidence regarding the effects of the SLAC on teacher's professional development, and the level of seriousness as regards on the problems encountered participating the SLAC.

Teachers' Perception s About the Conduct of the SLAC Sessions

Weight	Range	Category	Description
5	4.20 - 5.00	Highly Positive	Suggests a strong and positive affirmation of the effectiveness and value of the SLAC sessions
4	3.40 - 4.19	Positive	Reflects a positive stance toward the conduct of SLAC sessions
3	2.60 - 3.39	Neutral	Indicates a balanced or impartial stance on the conduct of SLAC sessions
2	1.80 - 2.59	Negative	Signals that there are areas that may need improvement or reconsideration in the way these SLAC sessions are conducted
1	1.00 - 1.79	Very Negative	Indicates that there are fundamental issues or shortcomings in the way these SLAC sessions are conducted

Perceived Effects of the SLAC on the Professional Development

Weight	Range	Category	Description
5	4.20 - 5.00	Highly Effective	Perceive a very pronounced and unmistakable effect of SLAC on your professional development.
4	3.40 - 4.19	Effective	Perceive a strong and clear effect of SLAC on your professional development.
3	2.60 - 3.39	Neutral	Perceive a noticeable effect of SLAC on your professional development.
2	1.80 - 2.59	Not Effective	Perceive a subtle or minimal effect of SLAC on your professional development.
1	1.00 - 1.79	Not Very Effective	Perceive a notable absence or no effect of SLAC on your professional development.

Ethical Consideration

The Declaration of Helsinki's guidelines were followed when conducting the study. The Helsinki Declaration provided ethical standards for studies involving identifiable human data and materials and medical research involving human subjects. For example, the researcher followed all ethical guidelines when giving the survey questionnaires to all teaching participants.

The study was accepted following the Cebu Technological University-Carmen Campus Research and Ethics Committee protocol. Adults voluntarily participated in the survey questionnaire as part of the study. An accompanying cover letter outlining the study's purpose and confidentiality, possible goals, and voluntary participation was provided before that. There were no monetary rewards for taking part in the research. The author disclosed no conflicts of interest.

DEFINITION OF TERMS

The following terms were operationally defined. There would be an ample explanation of the terms used technically and measurements utilized during data collection to further understand the study.

Effects of the SLAC. The term meant for any changes and effects that SLAC sessions had on faculty teaching methods, teamwork, and skills could be observed. These included deeper classroom performance, more competent behavior, and better approaches to instruction. In this study, the kinds of effects were found by looking at changes that teachers experienced or demonstrated after participating in SLAC sessions.

Enhanced SLAC Plan. An improved SLAC plan was a better version of the basic SLAC framework. It was created to make sure that learning activities were in line with current educational objectives and the specific needs of teachers as they grow. It had defined objectives, relevant material, and an outline for how to carry them out. This study examined at the quality, frequency, and effectiveness of SLAC sessions based on the improved plan.

Professional Development. Professional development was an ongoing procedure that helped teachers improved their capacity, knowledge, and approaches to make teaching and learning effective. It included both formal and informal activities like training, workshops, and collaborative learning, like SLAC. This study looked at how SLAC affiliation helped teachers grow professionally and use what they learn in the classroom.

SLAC. The School Learning Action Cell (SLAC) was a way for teachers to work together to improve their skills at school. They met regularly to share what they knew, thought about how they teach, and filled in any gaps in their students' learning. It was a place for ongoing learning, improving the curriculum, and improving how lessons were taught. In this study, SLAC stood for structured, school-led sessions that were meant for learning and teaching to be improved.

Teacher's Perceptions. Teacher's perceptions were their own thoughts, feelings, and ideas about how important, useful, and impactful SLAC sessions were. These ideas affected how involved they were and how willing they were to use what they learned in their teaching. This study used questionnaires and interviews to find out how SLAC affected their professional growth path.

Chapter 2

PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS, AND INTERPRETATION OF DATA

This section presented, analyzed, and interpreted the data gathered to examine the impact of the SLAC on the professional enhancement of secondary school teachers in the District of Carmen, Division of Cebu Province. It bridged the results obtained through the research instruments with the study's theoretical and conceptual framework, providing a comprehensive understanding of how SLAC influences teachers' growth and instructional practices. The discussion highlighted the implications of the findings, compared them with related studies and established theories, and identifies emerging insights relevant to school-based professional learning.

Each table in this section served a distinct purpose—whether describing the respondents' profile, illustrating teachers' perceptions of SLAC sessions, presenting significant differences across demographic variables, or revealing the relationships between perceptions and professional development outcomes. The accompanying narrative contextualized these tables, explained their significance, and guided readers through the results' interpretation against the study's objectives, hypotheses, and research questions.

PROFILE OF RESPONDENTS

The distribution of the teacher responders based on the highest level of education was shown in this section. The information represented the educational backgrounds of secondary school teachers in the Cebu Province Division's District of Carmen. Table 1 illustrates that despite a lower percentage of respondents had finished their MAEd, the majority had obtained master's degree courses. Only a few hold doctoral units or were candidates for a doctoral degree. The results showed that most teachers were actively grinding for higher education, demonstrating their commitment to professional growth and continuous learning. This trend suggested that the teaching force in the district were academically motivated and inclined toward advanced studies, supporting the Department of Education's thrust for sustained professional development and lifelong learning among educators.

Table 2. *Highest Educational Attainment*

Highest Educational Attainment	n	%
Bachelor's Degree	18	13.04
With Master's Units or CAR	104	75.36
Master's Degree	14	10.14
With Doctoral Units	1	.72
With Doctoral Degree or CAR	1	.72
TOTAL	138	100%

The data revealed that many high school teachers at the Carmen District holds Master's units or were currently completing their Master's degree (75.36%). Higher education was linked to enhanced teacher performance, implying that those pursuing master's degrees were likely to demonstrate better teaching effectiveness in their roles (Sariningsih & Komariah, 2021). This finding suggested that most respondents were pursuing higher education, indicating a strong desire for academic and professional growth. Only 10.14% had completed a Master's degree, while a minimal proportion hold Doctoral units or were candidates for a doctorate degree (0.72%). Meanwhile, 13.04% of respondents hold only a bachelor's degree, suggesting that although some teachers had not pursued graduate studies, the overall teaching force was highly inclined toward postgraduate studies. While many teachers joined the field with only a bachelor's degree, there was an obvious trend toward seeking further education as a form of professional development and a means to improve teaching practices and outcomes (Ayeni, 2012).

This trend implied that participation in Learning Action Cell (LAC) sessions complements teachers' continuing education by providing alternative, school-based professional learning opportunities. The results also supported the idea that schools like Carmen NHS had teachers who were transitioning from academic coursework to applied professional learning, which aligned with DepEd's emphasis on lifelong learning and career progression for educators.

Table 3. *Number of Years in Service*

Number of Years in Service	n	%
0-5 years	25	18.11
5-10 years	36	26.08
11-20 years	49	35.50
21 years above	28	20.28
TOTAL	138	100%

This section presented the number of respondents in relation to their length of teaching experience. The data provided an overview of the length of service of the participating secondary school teachers in the District of Carmen, Division of Cebu Province. As reflected in Table 3 the respondents represented various phases of their teaching careers, ranging from young educators with only a few years of experience to veteran teachers who had served for more than two decades. This classification helped in understanding how the diversity of experience may influence teachers' perceptions of the School Learning Action Cell (SLAC) sessions and their professional development. The findings enabled the study of whether years of teaching service contributed to differences in engagement, openness to collaboration, and responsiveness to professional learning initiatives.

In terms of teaching experience, the largest group of respondents (35.50%) had been in service for 11–20 years, followed by those with 5–10 years (26.08%) and those with 21 years or more (20.28%). These figures suggested that the school's teaching force was predominantly composed of seasoned educators who had likely been exposed to various professional development programs and classroom-based innovations (Aderibigbe, 2013). Seasoned educators, particularly those in mid-career stages, were often in a stronger position to leverage their accumulated experience to engage in and contribute to

collaborative professional development activities. Only 18.11 % were relatively new teachers with 0–5 years of experience. Hinson et al. (2023) found that peer-to-peer mentoring had a positive impact on initial teacher professional development, suggesting that such collaborative dynamics could effectively facilitate the sharing of expertise among seasoned educators and provide targeted support for new teachers. This distribution suggested that most of the participants were seasoned educators who had sufficient exposure to professional development activities and classroom-based innovations.

The domination of mid-career teachers (5 to 20 years in service) implied that the school’s teaching force was composed mainly of educators who were stable in their profession and were likely to benefit most from collaborative professional development models, such as LAC. Experienced teachers shared expertise, while early-career teachers learned through peer mentoring, aligning with the LAC framework’s collaborative learning approach. Such collaborative environments benefited from the wealth of knowledge shared by seasoned educators, ensuring that less experienced teachers gained from their expertise through mentoring opportunities (Hulpia et al., 2012; Klassen & Chiu, 2010).

Table 4. *Number of SLAC Attended*

Number of SLACS Attended	n	%
0-5	55	39.85
6-10	47	34.05
11-15	25	18.11
16-20	11	7.97
TOTAL	138	100%

This section presented the statistical number of respondents against the number of School Learning Action Cell (SLAC) sessions they attended. The data highlighted the extent of teachers’ participation in SLAC activities within the District of Carmen, Division of Cebu Province. As shown in Table 3, respondents vary in their level of engagement, with some attended only a few sessions while others participated more frequently. This classification provided insight into teachers’ exposure to collaborative learning experiences and school-based professional development initiatives. Examining the number of sessions attended helped determine whether number of times they participated influences teachers’ view of SLAC effectiveness and its contribution to their professional growth. The analysis also highlighted the importance of consistent participation in SLAC sessions as a means of promoting continuous improvement in teaching practices.

Regarding participation in School Learning Action Cell (SLAC) sessions, the data show that a significant portion (39.85%) of teachers attended 0–5 sessions, followed by those who attended 6–10 sessions (34.05%), 11–15 sessions (18.11%), and only 8% attended 16–20 sessions. While most teachers participated in LAC activities, the frequency of attendance varied significantly. This trend suggested a need for a deeper investigation into the factors influencing such attendance rates, including potential constraints such as workload, personal scheduling, and perceptions of the relevance of these sessions (Feng et al., 2024; Belay et al., 2022).

The relatively lower number of teachers attending more than ten sessions indicated constraints such as scheduling conflicts, workload, or varying perceptions of the LAC’s relevance. However, the high participation of those attending at least some sessions showed that the program had reached a substantial portion of the teaching force. This trend in attendance to SLAC sessions emphasized the need to strengthen teacher engagement and institutionalize regular SLAC sessions to ensure consistent participation. Despite this success, the need for institutional reinforcement of regular SLAC sessions was evident; continuous support mechanisms were crucial for sustaining teacher engagement over time (Balkar & Alev, 2022).

TEACHER'S PERCEPTION OF SLAC SESSIONS

This section presented the summary of responses from the teachers' perception of SLAC sessions. The questionnaire employed a Likert scale procedure with corresponding verbal interpretations. A mean score was also presented.

Table 5. *Teacher's Perception of SLAC Sessions*

Statements	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. Our SLAC sessions include topics on learner diversity and inclusion.	4.64	Highly Positive
2. Our SLAC sessions emphasize learners as the core of all education processes.	4.72	Highly Positive
3. Our SLAC sessions highlight the importance of understanding learner characteristics and experiences.	4.63	Highly Positive
4. Our SLAC sessions apply differentiated instruction to cater to varied learner needs.	4.61	Highly Positive
5. Our SLAC sessions implement developmentally-appropriate teaching methods respecting learner differences.	4.65	Highly Positive
6. Our SLAC sessions plan lessons and delivers instructions effectively.	4.59	Highly Positive
7. Our SLAC sessions share lessons and experiences to improve teaching practices	4.70	Highly Positive
8. Our SLAC sessions plan weekly lessons during LAC for a specified period.	4.25	Highly Positive
9. Our SLAC sessions implement learner-centered assessment policies aligned with K to 12 curriculum.	4.59	Highly Positive
10. Our SLAC sessions use formative assessment data to improve lesson delivery.	4.46	Highly Positive
11. Our SLAC sessions measure teaching effectiveness based on student results.	4.46	Highly Positive
12. Our SLAC sessions conduct assessments that provide feedback on learning outcomes	4.49	Highly Positive
General Assessment	4.57	Highly Positive

The results of the study indicated that teachers in the Carmen district had a highly favorable perception of the School Learning Action Cell (SLAC) sessions. The results showed that teachers firmly believe SLAC sessions were successful, with a general weighted mean of 4.57, which characterized as "Highly Positive." venues for professional growth and instructional improvement. Gabion & Despi (2025) highlighted how such collaborative frameworks empowered teachers and enhanced their instructional effectiveness, supporting the idea that SLAC sessions, due to their collaborative and reflective nature, are well-received by educators.

This high rating suggested that the sessions were well-organized, relevant, and responsive to teachers' needs. It reflected that SLAC activities successfully promote collaboration, reflective practice, and learner-centered teaching, all of which contributed to enhancing teachers' professional competence. The overall result suggested that SLAC sessions played a significant role in supporting continuous professional development, enabling teachers to improve their classroom practices, assessment literacy, and responsiveness to learner diversity. Swanson et al. (2022) illustrated that structured collaboration and reflective practices in professional development could lead to improve classroom performance.

PERCEIVED EFFECTIVENESS OF THE SLAC SESSIONS ON TEACHERS

This section presented the summary of responses from the teachers' perceived effectiveness of the SLAC sessions. The questionnaire employed a Likert scale procedure with corresponding verbal interpretations. A mean score was also presented.

Table 6. *Teacher's Perceived Effects on Teaching Practice*

Statements	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. The SLAC session improved my ability to deliver lesson content effectively.	4.41	Highly Effective
2. I am more confident in implementing differentiated instruction after attending SLAC sessions.	4.38	Highly Effective
3. SLAC discussions helped me align my teaching strategies with current curriculum standards.	4.48	Highly Effective
4. The session helped me address challenges I encounter in the classroom.	4.46	Highly Effective
5. I have become more reflective about my teaching practices as a result of SLAC participation.	4.42	Highly Effective
6. SLAC sessions enhanced my ability to assess student learning more effectively.	4.44	Highly Effective
7. I have adopted new teaching methods shared by colleagues during SLAC discussions.	4.43	Highly Effective
8. SLAC sessions encouraged me to integrate more learner-centered approaches in my classroom.	4.49	Highly Effective
General Assessment	4.44	Highly Effective

The findings revealed that the perceived effects of SLAC sessions on teachers' professional development were highly effective, as shown by the general weighted mean of 4.44. This indicated that teachers strongly recognized the positive impact of SLAC participation on their instructional competence, efficacy, and reflective practice. Bajar et al. (2021) findings showed that teachers associated professional learning settings with enhanced reflective practice, supporting a greater sense of competence in lesson delivery.

The results suggested that teachers viewed SLAC sessions as highly effective learning platforms that enhanced their ability to deliver lessons, adopt new teaching strategies, and aligned classroom practices with current curriculum standards. Datumaas et al. (2024) proposed a conceptual model for SLAC implementation, emphasizing its cost-effectiveness and the positive impact on teacher collaboration and innovation. Moreover, the high mean ratings across all indicators reflected that SLAC sessions foster collaboration and innovation, enabling teachers to share best practices and apply learner-centered approaches in their classrooms. Penuel et al. (2007) supported these claims by demonstrating that effective professional development, characterized by coherence and active engagement, lead to improved instructional practice and increased teaching effectiveness across various educational contexts.

THE EFFECTIVENESS OF TEACHERS' PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT

This section presented the summary of responses from the teachers' perceived effectiveness on their professional development. The questionnaire employed a Likert scale procedure with corresponding verbal interpretations. A mean score was also presented.

Table 7. *Effectiveness of Teachers' Professional Development*

Statements	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. The SLAC sessions motivated me to pursue further professional learning.	4.45	Highly Effective

2. I have developed better collaboration skills as a result of participating in SLAC.	4.52	Highly Effective
3. The sessions have contributed to my career growth as a professional educator.	4.55	Highly Effective
4. SLAC activities have enhanced my ability to reflect on and assess my teaching practices.	4.48	Highly Effective
5. SLAC sessions encouraged me to participate in other professional development programs or trainings.	4.51	Highly Effective
6. I have become more proactive in sharing best practices with my colleagues after attending SLAC.	4.39	Highly Effective
7. My involvement in SLAC strengthened my commitment to lifelong learning as a teacher.	4.55	Highly Effective
8. The sessions empowered me to take on leadership roles within my school or department	4.39	Highly Effective
General Assessment	4.48	Highly Effective

The results showed that the perceived effects of SLAC sessions on teachers' professional development were highly effective, with a general weighted mean of 4.44. The overall positive rating of SLAC sessions highlighted their effectiveness in improving lesson delivery and aligning instructional strategies with curriculum standards (Bajar et al., 2021). This strongly affirmed that teachers recognize the significant contribution of SLAC to their growth as educators.

The high overall rating indicated that SLAC sessions helped teachers improve lesson delivery, aligned strategies with curriculum standards, adopted innovative practices, and reflected more deeply on their teaching methods. Moreover, it had been highlighted that well-structured professional development sessions enhanced teachers' confidence and instructional mastery, akin to the experiences attributed to SLAC participation (Bowling et al., 2024; Rennie, 2011). The consistency of "Highly Effective" responses across indicators highlighted that the program was not only relevant but also highly effective in enhancing professional competence. These findings collectively suggested that SLAC and similar collaborative frameworks had a considerable influence on educators' professional growth and instructional effectiveness, underscoring their critical role in the educational landscape (Caballes, 2023).

The findings emphasized that SLAC had become a powerful platform for continuous professional learning, teachers were equipped with skills, confidence, and reflective practices needed to address classroom challenges and promote learner-centered instruction.

THE EFFECTIVENESS OF STUDENTS' LEARNING

This section presented the summary of responses from the teachers' perceived effectiveness of SLAC sessions on students' learning. The questionnaire employed a Likert scale procedure with corresponding verbal interpretations. A mean score was also presented.

Table 8. Responses on the Effectiveness of Students' Learning

Statements	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. Students show increased engagement in class after I applied strategies discussed in SLAC.	4.15	Effective
2. My participation in SLAC has helped improve student learning outcomes.	4.28	Highly Effective

3. There has been a noticeable improvement in student behavior as a result of my SLAC-based interventions.	4.19	Effective
4. SLAC sessions supported my ability to create more inclusive learning environments.	4.41	Highly Effective
5. The teaching techniques I learned from SLAC sessions have increased student participation during class activities.	4.31	Highly Effective
6. SLAC sessions enabled me to better address diverse learning needs in my classroom.	4.41	Highly Effective
7. My use of SLAC-informed strategies has helped students become more independent and self-motivated learners.	4.27	Highly Effective
8. Students have shown improved collaboration and peer interaction in group activities since I applied SLAC strategies.	4.33	Highly Effective
General Assessment	4.29	Highly Effective

The results revealed that the effectiveness of SLAC sessions on students' learning was highly effective, as reflected in the general weighted mean of 4.29. Complementary evidence from Wolff et al. (2010) further substantiated the connection between effective professional development and higher student academic achievement, demonstrating that well-designed teacher training results in more effective instructional strategies grounded in scientific research. This result signified that teachers observed substantial improvements in their students' engagement, participation, and overall learning outcomes after implementing SLAC-informed strategies.

The high overall rating implies that SLAC sessions had effectively equipped teachers with learner-centered and inclusive teaching approaches, enabling them to address diverse learning needs and foster active classroom participation. Zheng et al. (2024) illustrated that when teachers adopted methods that empower students to actively engage and think critically, learning outcomes improved respectively. The "Highly Effective" interpretation across most indicators suggested that SLAC discussions translated into tangible student improvements, particularly in behavior, motivation, and collaboration. These collective results did not only improved academic outcomes but also cultivated intrinsic motivation among students crucial for sustained participation in their learning journeys (Fatmawati et al., 2025; , Rahayu et al., 2020).

OVERALL EFFECTIVENESS OF SLAC SESSIONS

This section presented the summary of responses from the teachers' perceived overall effectiveness of SLAC sessions. The questionnaire employed a Likert scale procedure with corresponding verbal interpretations. A mean score was also presented.

Table 9. Overall Effectiveness of SLAC Sessions

Statements	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. SLAC sessions are relevant to the needs of our school community.	4.54	Highly Effective
2. The frequency and scheduling of SLAC sessions are appropriate.	4.42	Highly Effective
3. The quality of facilitation during SLAC sessions meets my expectations.	4.34	Highly Effective
4. SLAC has become an integral part of our school's continuous improvement efforts.	4.53	Highly Effective

5. The objectives of each SLAC session are clearly communicated and well understood.	4.53	Highly Effective
6. SLAC sessions effectively foster a culture of professional dialogue and shared responsibility.	4.53	Highly Effective
7. I find the outputs and action plans from SLAC sessions useful and actionable.	4.44	Highly Effective
8. The SLAC sessions have contributed to a more collaborative and supportive school environment.	4.54	Highly Effective
General Assessment	4.48	Highly Effective

The findings showed that the overall effectiveness of SLAC sessions was rated as highly effective, with a general weighted mean of 4.48. Lugu (2023) demonstrated that when professional development sessions were purposefully designed and aligned with the school's needs, teachers were more likely to perceive them as beneficial for their professional growth. The result indicated that teachers strongly affirmed the relevance, organization, and quality of SLAC implementation in their school. The consistently high mean scores reflected that the sessions were well-facilitated, purpose-driven, and conformed to the school community's needs. SLAC sessions promoted reflective dialogue, peer collaboration, and shared accountability, thereby fostering an environment conducive to continuous school improvement (Bajar et al., 2021).

The "Highly Effective" interpretation implied that SLAC had become an integral component of professional learning and school improvement, fostering collaboration, reflective dialogue, and shared accountability among teachers. The high rating on indicators such as relevance to school needs (4.54), clarity of objectives (4.53), and contribution to a collaborative school environment (4.54) further reinforced that SLAC was functioning effectively as a school-based professional development mechanism. Datumaas et al. (2024) confirmed that SLAC sessions were recognized by educational authorities as a cost-efficient and strategic mechanism for achieving professional development goals.

SIGNIFICANT DIFFERENCE BETWEEN TEACHERS' PERCEPTION OF LAC SESSIONS AND THEIR HIGHEST EDUCATIONAL ATTAINMENT, NUMBER OF YEARS IN SERVICE, AND NUMBER OF SLAC SESSIONS ATTENDED

This section presented the summary of results from ANOVA tests on the significant difference between teachers' perception of SLAC sessions and their highest educational attainment, years of teaching, and number of SLAC sessions attended. A P-value was shown in the table as to whether the variables were Significant or Not Significant.

Table 10. *Table Summary of Significant Difference Between Teachers' Perception of SLAC Sessions and Their Highest Educational Attainment, Years of Teaching, and Number of SLAC Sessions Attended*

Variable	Df	P-value	Decision
Highest Educational Attainment	4	0.020	Significant
Years of Teaching	4	0.003	Significant
Number of LAC Sessions Attended	3	0.596	Not Significant

An analysis of variance (ANOVA) was conducted to find out whether teachers' perceptions of the Learning Action Cell (LAC) sessions differed significantly when grouped according to their highest level of educational attainment. The results showed that the groups differed statistically significantly

($F(4,133) = 3.01, p = 0.020$). indicating that educational attainment influences teachers' perceptions of LAC sessions. Liu (2021) demonstrated that higher educational attainment in teachers is associated with increased cognitive abilities and professional expectations, which translated into more critical appraisals of professional development interventions such as LAC sessions.

To further identify where the differences occurred, a Bonferroni post hoc test was performed. The results showed that teachers with Doctoral Units or Candidate for Academic Requirements (CAR) reported significantly lower perceptions of LAC sessions compared with teachers holding Master's Units/CAR ($p = 0.031$), Master's Degree ($p = 0.025$), another Master's Units/CAR group ($p = 0.012$), and Bachelor's Degree ($p = 0.014$). Cebe and Suson (2023) found that educational attainment was a significant factor in shaping teachers' readiness and perceptions regarding curriculum delivery and instructional innovation. These studies suggested that teachers with doctoral-level credentials or units were likely to have more stringent evaluative criteria compared to those holding bachelor's or master's qualifications, which supported the reported outcome that teachers with advanced doctoral units reported significantly lower perceptions of the LAC sessions.

Meanwhile, there was no significant differences found among teachers with Bachelor's degrees, Master's degrees, or Master's units/CAR, suggesting that their perceptions of LAC sessions were relatively consistent. The results suggested that teachers pursuing or holding doctoral units had higher expectations for professional development activities, such as LAC sessions, which might lead to comparatively lower satisfaction or perception scores. In contrast, teachers with bachelor's and master's level qualifications appeared to hold more positive and uniform perceptions of the program.

To find out if teacher perceptions of the LAC sessions varied significantly based on their years of teaching experience, analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used. A statistically significant difference between the groups was found in the results ($F(4,133) = 4.29, p = 0.003$), indicating that teaching experience influences how teachers perceive LAC sessions. This pattern was further validated by studies that had found that demographic factors, including years of teaching experience, often served as moderators in how teachers engage with and value professional development opportunities (Al-Salamat, 2024).

The estimated marginal means showed that teachers with 0–5 years ($M = 4.72$) and 5–10 years ($M = 4.71$) of teaching experience reported the highest levels of positive perception of LAC sessions. According to Ünal and Ünal (2023), novice and early-career teachers exhibited more positive attitudes toward innovative educational strategies compared to their more experienced peers. This was followed by those with 11–20 years ($M = 4.53$), while the lowest ratings were observed among teachers with 21 years and above ($M = 4.32$). These findings supported the notion that tailored professional development models, such as LAC sessions, may need to account for differences in perceptions based on teachers' career stages (Ockerman & Bagui, 2024).

To further identify where the differences occurred, Bonferroni post hoc comparisons were performed. The results revealed that significant differences existed between the 5–10 years and 21 years and above ($p = 0.007$), as well as between the 0–5 years and 21 years and above groups ($p = 0.015$). Such differences might be understood in light of research that showed veteran teachers, while experienced, sometimes demonstrated resistance toward adopting new educational practices, it was a phenomenon that influenced their overall perception of such programs (Little, 2009; Loucks-Horsley et al., 2010). Specifically, teachers with fewer years of experience (0–10 years) perceived LAC sessions more positively compared to their counterparts with over 21 years of teaching experience. There were no significant differences observed among the other group comparisons. These findings coincided with the notion that novice teachers were generally more enthusiastic about adopting new instructional methods and participating in innovative professional development activities (Brown & Lee, 2019).

These findings suggested that novice and early-career teachers tend to value LAC sessions more positively than highly experienced teachers. This might be attributed to the fact that younger teachers were more open to collaborative learning and professional development opportunities, whereas seasoned teachers might perceive these sessions as less beneficial, possibly due to their accumulated teaching experiences or established teaching practices.

An analysis of variance (ANOVA) was conducted to determine whether teachers' perceptions of the LAC sessions differed significantly when grouped according to the number of SLACs attended. The results of the ANOVA revealed that the effect of the number of SLACs attended was not statistically significant, $F(3, 134) = 0.631$, $p = 0.596$. Mohammadi and Moradi (2017) found that when critical variables in teacher professional development were controlled, participants' perceptions tend not to differ substantially, thereby reinforcing the current finding. This suggests that the teachers' perceptions of the LAC sessions did not vary based on the number of sessions they had attended.

Badri et al., (2016) noted that effective professional development programs were designed to provide all participants with similar high-quality learning and collaboration opportunities, ensuring that even teachers with fewer sessions could perceive and benefit from the intended outcomes. On the other hand, Altaf and Saeed (2020) reported that teacher perceptions regarding national professional standards did not differ significantly across varying demographic or participation levels, reinforcing the idea that standardized delivery could minimize variation in outcomes. Professional development trainings aimed to deliver quality high standard sessions to cater all types of professionals.

The findings implied that teachers consistently perceived the LAC sessions positively, regardless of frequency of participation. One possible explanation was that the sessions were conducted in a standardized manner, providing the same quality of learning and collaboration opportunities to participants across different groups. This result also suggested that even teachers who had attended fewer sessions were able to recognize the benefits of LAC participation, aligning with the goal of LAC to promote professional collaboration and shared learning experiences among educators.

SIGNIFICANT RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN TEACHERS' PERCEPTION OF SLAC SESSIONS AND PERCEIVED EFFECTS ON TEACHING PRACTICE, EFFECTIVENESS ON PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT, EFFECTIVENESS OF STUDENTS' LEARNING, AND OVERALL EFFECTIVENESS OF SLAC SESSIONS

This section presented the summary of Pearson r 's results on the relationship test between teachers' perception of SLAC Sessions and perceived effects on their teaching practice, effectiveness on professional development, effectiveness of students' learning, and overall effectiveness of SLAC sessions.

Table 11. *Summary Table of Correlation Between Teachers' Perception of LAC Sessions and the following variables*

Variable	Pearson's r	Strength of Relationship	P-Value	Decision
Perceived effects on teaching practice	0.766	Strong positive correlation	<.001	Significant
Effectiveness on professional development	0.742	Strong positive correlation	<.001	Significant
Effectiveness of Students' Learning	0.709	Strong positive correlation	<.001	Significant

Overall effectiveness of SLAC Sessions	0.811	Very strong positive correlation	<.001	Very Significant
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The relationship between teacher perceptions of the LAC sessions and their perceived impact on their teaching practice was investigated using a Pearson product–moment correlation. The two variables showed a significant positive association, according to the analysis $r(136) = .766, p < .001$. Santos (2023) noted that participation in LAC sessions correlated positively with teachers' self-identified competencies, indicating that the collaborative nature of SLACs not only facilitated skill development but also reinforced their professional identities and effectiveness in teaching. This suggested that higher levels of positive perceptions of the LAC sessions were associated with a greater perceived impact on teaching practice.

The results suggested that teachers who viewed LAC sessions more positively tend to perceive them as more beneficial for their professional growth. The strong and significant correlation supported the assumption that LAC sessions played a crucial role in enhancing teachers' competencies, skills, and overall professional development. The finding aligned with the purpose of the LAC framework, which was to foster collaborative learning among teachers and improve teaching practices through shared experiences. Khumalo (2019) confirmed that leadership frameworks that promote collaborative practices, such as LACs, significantly enhanced teacher commitment, ultimately fostering better educational outcomes and professional satisfaction.

The implication was that sustained and well-implemented LAC sessions contributed not only to improved teacher perceptions but also to tangible developmental outcomes in secondary school contexts. Future studies further explored the causal mechanisms by incorporating qualitative measures or longitudinal designs to determine how specific elements of LAC sessions influence teacher development over time.

The relationship between teachers' perception of the LAC sessions and their perceived effectiveness on professional development was examined using Pearson product–moment correlation. The findings showed that the two variables had a substantial positive connection ($r(136) = 0.742, p < .001$). This implied that teachers who had a favorable view of the LAC sessions also tended to claim that these sessions were more successful in advancing their professional development. According to Santos (2023), positive appraisal of LAC sessions, characterized by collaborative dialogue, shared best practices, and reflective discussion, directly influences teachers' perception of these sessions as effective instruments for professional development.

The finding suggested that teachers' perceptions of the quality and value of LAC sessions significantly influenced how effective they view these sessions in enhancing their professional growth. The strong correlation confirmed the alternative hypothesis (H_a) that a positive relationship existed between the two variables. This result was consistent with prior research, which highlighted that professional learning communities, such as LAC sessions, play a vital role in fostering teacher collaboration, reflection, and continuous improvement. Ganiban (2023) explored the formulation of a localized LAC framework and suggested that when educators perceived the quality and facilitative aspects of these sessions positively, they reported enhanced professional development outcomes. When teachers viewed these sessions positively, they were more likely to maximize learning opportunities, which in turn led to stronger professional development outcomes.

Meanwhile, another correlation analysis was conducted to determine the relationship between teachers' perceptions of the LAC sessions and their perceived effectiveness on student learning. As shown on table 11, the computed Pearson's r is 0.709, with a p -value $< .001$ at $df = 136$. Santos (2023) demonstrated that participation in LAC sessions led to improved teaching competencies, thereby positively impacting student outcomes. This showed that the two variables had a significant positive

association. Since the correlation was statistically significant at the $p < .001$ level, the null hypothesis of no relationship was rejected. Studies in professional development underscored that well-conceived and effectively implemented initiatives, such as LAC sessions, enhanced teacher practices and improved student learning outcomes (Desimone, 2009).

This finding indicated that students' learning and teachers' perceived efficacy were significantly correlated with more positive opinions of the LAC sessions. In practical terms, the findings highlighted that LAC sessions, as professional learning mechanisms, were not only valued by teachers but were also believed to directly enhance student learning outcomes. These findings reinforced the importance of sustaining and improving LAC sessions as part of school-based professional development programs to maximize their impact on instructional practices and student achievement.

In order to ascertain the connection between teachers' opinions on the LAC sessions and the general efficacy of the SLAC sessions, a correlation analysis was finally carried out. The results revealed a strong positive correlation between the two variables, $r(136) = 0.811, p < .001$. Culajara (2023) suggested that the subjective experience of a well-delivered LAC session predisposed teachers to perceive further professional development interventions, such as SLAC sessions, more favorably. This indicated that teachers who held favorable perceptions about the LAC sessions were also more likely to rate the SLAC sessions as effective overall.

Since the obtained correlation coefficient was both high and statistically significant at the 0.001 level, the alternative hypothesis is supported. This finding suggested that the quality of teachers' experiences and perceptions during LAC sessions substantially influences how effective they perceived SLAC sessions to be. Research exploring teacher perceptions within professional development contexts demonstrated that these perceptions were predictive of broader evaluations of session effectiveness (Ockerman & Bagui, 2024).

This result aligned with the idea that collaborative learning communities enhanced professional growth and instructional effectiveness. When teachers positively engaged in LAC activities, they see these sessions as meaningful, relevant, and impactful to their professional practice. The strong relationship underscored the importance of maintaining well-structured, responsive, and participatory LAC sessions to maximize their perceived effectiveness.

Chapter 3

SUMMARY OF FINDINGS, CONCLUSIONS, & RECOMMENDATIONS

SUMMARY OF FINDINGS

The study revealed that the majority of the respondents, representing 75.36%, had earned units toward a master's degree, while 10.14% had already completed their master's program, and only 0.72% had doctoral units. In terms of teaching experience, 35.50% of the teachers had been in service for 11 to 20 years, 26.08% for 5 to 10 years, and 20.28% for more than 21 years. Meanwhile, 39.85% of the respondents attended 0–5 School Learning Action Cell (SLAC) sessions, 34.05% attended 6–10 sessions, and 18.11% participated in 11–15 sessions, indicating varying levels of engagement among teachers.

Findings further revealed that teachers strongly agreed ($M = 4.57$) that SLAC sessions foster learner-centered, reflective, and collaborative teaching practices. The sessions were viewed as highly relevant and responsive to their instructional needs, supporting the goal of continuous professional development. The perceived effects of SLAC participation on teachers' professional development were rated as *Extremely Evident* ($M = 4.44$), demonstrating that SLAC sessions have helped improve instructional delivery, confidence, reflective practice, and assessment literacy. Moreover, participation in SLAC strengthened teachers' commitment to lifelong learning and professional collaboration.

Results of the analysis of variance (ANOVA) indicated significant differences in teachers' perceptions when grouped according to educational attainment ($p = 0.020$) and years of teaching experience ($p = 0.003$). Teachers with doctoral units reported less favorable perceptions compared to those with lower academic qualifications, while early-career teachers expressed more positive views than those with over 21 years of experience. However, no significant difference was observed when respondents were grouped according to the number of SLAC sessions attended ($p = 0.596$), implying that teachers generally held consistent views regardless of their frequency of participation.

Furthermore, a strong positive correlation was found between teachers' perceptions of SLAC sessions and various measures of effectiveness. Specifically, perceptions were significantly related to professional development ($r = 0.766$, $p < .001$), effectiveness on professional development ($r = 0.742$, $p < .001$), and student learning ($r = 0.709$, $p < .001$). These results suggested that teachers who hold favorable perceptions of SLAC sessions were more likely to experience higher levels of professional growth and contribute to improved student learning outcomes.

CONCLUSION

School Learning Action Cell (SLAC) served as a highly effective mechanism for fostering professional growth among secondary school teachers. It had been instrumental in promoting collaboration, innovation, and reflective practice within the teaching community. The findings revealed that teachers' educational attainment and years of experience significantly influenced their perceptions of SLAC, suggesting that professional background and length of service shaped how educators value school-based learning initiatives. However, the number of SLAC sessions attended was found to have no significant effect, implying that teachers maintained consistently positive views regardless of their frequency of participation. Moreover, teachers' favorable perceptions of SLAC were strongly associated with enhanced professional competencies, reflective teaching practices, and improved student learning outcomes.

RECOMMENDATIONS

From the findings, school administrators and education leaders should continue and institutionalize School Learning Action Cell (SLAC) sessions as a systematic vehicle for ongoing professional development. Efforts should focus on ensuring that SLAC activities remained responsive, learner-centered, and reflective, aligning with teachers' diverse educational backgrounds and levels of experience.

Additionally, mentorship programs were introduced to bridge perceptual gaps between early-career and veteran teachers, promoting shared learning and innovation. The Department of Education (DepEd) might consider integrating SLAC participation into teacher evaluation and promotion systems to reinforce commitment to professional growth.

Recommendations For Further Studies

1. "Enhancing the Effectiveness of School Learning Action Cells: A Longitudinal, Comparative, and Qualitative Research Agenda"
2. "School Learning Action Cells and Teacher Development: Long-Term Impacts, Contextual Variations, and Lived Experiences"
3. "Understanding the Success of School Learning Action Cells: Leadership, Organizational Culture, and Pedagogical Outcomes"
4. "Innovating School Learning Action Cells: The Role of Technology, Leadership, and Institutional Support in Teacher Learning"

5. “Strengthening Teacher Professional Learning through School Learning Action Cells: Evidence, Challenges, and Future Directions”

Chapter 4

OUTPUT OF THE STUDY

“Enhanced School Learning Action Cell (SLAC) Program for Sustained Professional Growth of Secondary Teachers”

GOALS

The results of the study clearly revealed that the School Learning Action Cell (SLAC) served as a vital platform for teachers’ professional development, promoting collaboration, reflective practice, and instructional innovation. However, while teachers in the District of Carmen displayed strong agreement on the effectiveness of SLAC sessions, variations in perception emerged across educational attainment and years of teaching experience. This suggested that while SLAC had been impactful, there remained a need to enhance its inclusivity, consistency, and contextualization to address the diverse professional learning needs of teachers.

An enhanced SLAC program was therefore essential to ensure that every session became a dynamic avenue for shared learning, inquiry-based reflection, and evidence-informed practice. The program will integrate differentiated learning experiences tailored to teachers’ career stages—from novice educators to senior mentors—and will align with the Department of Education’s (DepEd) mandate for continuing professional development through school-based learning. Furthermore, it seeks to strengthen teacher participation and accountability by providing structured opportunities for collaborative planning, mentoring, and action research, thereby making professional learning more meaningful and sustained.

By institutionalizing a more comprehensive and systematic SLAC framework, schools can cultivate a community of practice where teachers are empowered to co-create solutions to instructional challenges, share innovations, and align their teaching strategies with curriculum standards. The enhanced program also aims to deepen the link between professional growth and student achievement by ensuring that all SLAC activities directly contribute to improving learning outcomes. Ultimately, this initiative will serve as a blueprint for continuous teacher development and school improvement within the district.

OBJECTIVES

1. To strengthen teacher engagement, participation, and ownership in SLAC sessions;
2. To provide differentiated, research-based, and needs-responsive SLAC content aligned with teachers’ experience levels;
3. To foster a culture of collaboration, mentoring, and reflective practice among educators;
4. To integrate classroom-based action research into SLAC discussions to address context-specific challenges;
5. To establish systematic evaluation tools to measure SLAC’s impact on teacher performance and student learning outcomes.

METHODS

The enhanced SLAC program will be implemented through five structured phases over the course of one school year to ensure that professional learning remains continuous, collaborative, and outcome-driven.

In Phase 1: Orientation and Capacity Building (Month 1), an orientation will be conducted for school heads, SLAC coordinators, and teacher-leaders to clarify objectives, expected outcomes, and

implementation strategies. Training sessions will also be provided on SLAC facilitation, collaborative inquiry, and reflective dialogue. During this phase, each school will establish a SLAC core team responsible for leading topic selection and overseeing implementation and monitoring activities.

In Phase 2: Needs Assessment and Program Design (Month 2), a baseline survey and focus group discussions will be administered to identify teachers' learning needs based on their teaching experience, subject area, and performance indicators. SLAC topics will then be aligned with DepEd's Key Result Areas (KRAs), the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST), and the school's improvement priorities. A comprehensive year-long SLAC plan will be developed, outlining thematic schedules, expected outputs, and designated facilitators.

During Phase 3: Implementation of SLAC Sessions (Months 3–10), regular SLAC sessions will be conducted either monthly or bi-monthly. These sessions will focus on key areas such as differentiated instruction, inclusive education, assessment literacy, ICT integration, and research-based pedagogy. A variety of interactive strategies like lesson study, peer coaching, case analysis, and microteaching will be employed to ensure active participation. Teachers will be encouraged to record their insights, reflections, and best practices through SLAC journals. Collaborative action research projects addressing instructional challenges and learner needs will also be integrated during this phase.

Phase 4: Monitoring, Mentoring, and Support, which will run throughout the program, will focus on guiding and evaluating the implementation process. School heads and master teachers will serve as mentors to ensure that SLAC learnings are effectively applied in classroom instruction. Mid-year and quarterly reviews will be conducted to monitor program fidelity and teacher participation. Observation tools and self-assessment forms will be used to track professional growth, while inter-school sharing sessions or learning showcases will be organized to highlight best practices and success stories.

Finally, Phase 5: Evaluation and Sustainability (Months 11–12) will involve post-assessment surveys to determine the program's perceived effectiveness and developmental outcomes. Findings and outputs will be presented in a culminating activity or a district-wide SLAC summit to recognize outstanding initiatives. Based on the evaluation results and feedback, SLAC plans will be revised and enhanced to promote sustainability and continuous improvement in the succeeding implementation cycles.

The enhanced SLAC program is expected to generate significant outcomes at the individual, institutional, and learner levels.

For teachers, the program is anticipated to improve instructional competence and confidence, particularly in implementing learner-centered approaches. It will help develop reflective habits through the use of SLAC journals and peer feedback mechanisms, allowing teachers to continuously assess and refine their practices. Participation in school-based research and mentoring activities is also expected to increase, as teachers become more engaged in collaborative professional learning. Moreover, the program aims to cultivate a stronger commitment among educators to lifelong learning and teamwork, reinforcing a culture of shared responsibility and continuous improvement.

For schools, the program will contribute to the institutionalization of SLAC practices as a core component of the school's professional development plan. Comprehensive documentation—including meeting minutes, outputs, and action plans—will be systematically produced to ensure transparency and accountability. The program will also strengthen professional learning communities, encouraging teachers to work collaboratively toward shared goals. Additionally, schools are expected to develop a repository of contextualized teaching exemplars and innovative strategies that can serve as reference materials for future SLAC sessions and classroom practices.

For learners, the enhanced SLAC program is expected to result in greater classroom engagement and participation as teachers apply improved instructional techniques. Lessons will become more inclusive and responsive to diverse learning needs, ensuring that all students are given equal opportunities to

succeed. Ultimately, these improvements are projected to lead to better academic outcomes that align with the school's performance indicators and educational goals.

For the division and community, the program will serve as a replicable SLAC model that other districts within the Department of Education (DepEd) Cebu Province can adopt. It will promote a culture of evidence-based professional learning, where data and reflective practice guide instructional decisions. Over time, the program is expected to contribute to sustained improvements in teaching quality and overall school effectiveness, thereby strengthening the educational landscape of the district and beyond.

TRAINING MATRIX

Remarks						
Actual Accomplishment						
Expected Outcomes	Teachers demonstrate clear understanding of SLAC objectives and processes	Activity-based and learner-centered lesson plans developed	Teachers maintain reflection journals and improve assessment practices	Completed and approved action research proposals	Inclusive instructional plans implemented in classrooms	ICT-integrated lesson plans and classroom application
Time Frame	Session (1 Month)	Session (2 Month)	Session (3 Month)	Session (4 Month)	Session (5 Month)	Session 6 (Month 3–4)
Source of Budget	MOOE	MOOE	MOOE	MOOE	MOOE	MOOE / ICT Grant
Budget	Minimal	Minimal	Minimal	Minimal	Minimal	Moderate
Persons Involved	SLAC Coordinator, Teachers	Master Teacher, Subject Teachers	Department Head, Teachers	Research Focal Person, Teachers	Guidance Counselor, Teachers	ICT Coordinator, Teachers
Strategies	Lecture–discussion, workshop	Group discussion, demonstration teaching	Case analysis, peer feedback	Guided research mentoring	Collaborative planning	Hands-on ICT workshop
Objectives	Familiarize teachers with SLAC goals and structure	Enhance learner-centered teaching strategies	Improve teachers' self-evaluation and assessment skills	Develop research-based instructional interventions	Promote inclusive and equitable learning environments	Apply appropriate technology tools in instruction
Areas of Concern	Limited understanding of SLAC purpose and framework	Low learner engagement in classroom instruction	Limited reflective teaching and assessment practices	Weak integration of action research in teaching	Challenges in addressing diverse learner needs	Limited use of ICT in teaching and learning

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